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A Buried Motive behind a Murder

“Let us learn to dream, gentlemen, and then we may perhaps find the truth.” (Bressler 88). According to Freud, dreams are one of the ways used by the unconscious part of the mind to partially fulfill a repressed wish, especially an infantile one. The best way, Freud declares, to uncover the hidden wishes of the unconscious is through the analysis of dreams. He also maintains that a work of art should be treated exactly like a dream for both of them are ways to quench the flames of hidden desires of the unconscious. Hence, in order to dig beneath the surface motive of Mrs. Wright killing her husband, in *Susan Glaspell's The Trifles*, and shed light upon one of the real motives underlying the criminal act, this paper is well-equipped with Freudian psychoanalytic theory.

From the dawn of civilization, women are considered inferior and men are superior. Women's job is to serve their dominant males without any complaint. They are always considered a second class and men a first class in the society. The beginning of *The Trifles* clearly shows this when *County Attorney* addresses the women, who “have come in slowly and stand close together near the door,” “Come up to the fire, ladies.” A very conspicuous excretion of males' dominance over females, and females in return obey with closed eyes the commands of males. *Mrs. Wright*, the protagonist who kills her husband in Susan Glaspell's *The Trifles*, is presented as a submissive, subordinate creature that is stripped away of its freedom and identity and as a result kills its oppressor. Indeed, not only Mrs. Wright but also all of the women in the story faces the same situation. “I want to get the lay of things upstairs now” this is a man, *County Attorney*, speaking of getting upstairs, higher, and women are to remain downstairs, lower. In other words, the setting is a male-dominated territory where women have no freewill. Therefore, Mrs. Wright is the voice of all women, even the author herself, who seek a way out of this dungeon. They are all striving to get their freedom back from the tyrannous rule of men and thus a crime is to be committed.

A woman kills her husband after thirty years of their marriage in order to relief herself from his tyranny. From the very beginning, the story presents the man-woman conflict that exists in both the fictional story and real life. This conflict, according to Freud, is the result of an imaginary, sexual conflict that all of us go through at the stage of childhood.

Both males and females go through such a conflict, culminating with Oedipus complex. This experience varies from males to females in that women, Mrs. Wright in this case, go through what Freud dubbed penis envy and males through castration complex (Wright 14-15). What is at stake here is penis envy for, psychologically speaking; it is the real motive behind the murder.

Every now and then, a disguised word manages to escape the strict censor of the ego in order to partially gratify the repressed wish of a woman who suffers from penis envy, the unfulfilled desire for a phallus, authority. Mrs. Hale tells Mrs. Peters about the bad life of Mrs. Wright and how “she couldn’t do her part...” which is to beget a child through sexual intercourse. Having a child, according to Freud, would appease her complex and reduce the mental disturbance. Another reference to her desire of having a child is the word “apron” when Mrs. Peters says, “She said she wanted an apron.” Apron strings, which means the relationship between a mother and her child, is a farfetched dream for a wretched woman because her husband, John Wright, would not allow it.

The image of the bird killed and taken out of its cage in the story is an obvious link to her flaming desire of getting a child. Since “The drives and wishes can get through in disguise...” we can say that the bird symbolizes her wish for a male child because the it represents male authority. The comparison made between the canary and Mrs. Wright forces us to think of it as her child, especially when Mrs. Hale notes about Mrs. Wright that “she used to sing real pretty herself” and that “she was kind of like a bird herself—real sweet and pretty, but kind of timid and-fluttery.” Psychologically speaking, it is very normal to wind up with someone who looks like your parents; therefore, the similarity between Mrs. Wright and the canary is that of a mother and her child.

The bird of necessity requires a cage to live in and since the bird is a symbol of a child, then the cage becomes a symbol of a womb. The cage and the womb image is further clarified when Mrs. Peters says, “seems funny to think of a bird here. But she must have had one, or why would she have a cage?” Mrs. Wright, as a woman, has to fulfill her duty in begetting a child in order to be herself, a woman. Nature gives her a womb in order to have a child that gives her an identity and purpose. However, she has approached menopause now because she is perhaps, approximately speaking, fifty years old since she married thirty years ago, and she is no longer able to have a male child.

Another visual image of Mrs. Wright’s inability to fulfill herself throughout pregnancy is drawn when Mrs. Hale says, “It’s a shame about her fruit. I wonder if it is all gone.” She is sympathizing with Mrs. Wright incapability of having children anymore. Her ‘fruit’, which is “...in both Hebrew and classical tradition the fruit is associated with sexual love...” (Ferber 13) is rotten and no longer desired as Mrs. Peters exclaims, “Oh, her fruit; it did freeze.” The flames of desire and amorous have been put off. The repetition of the word ‘cold’ throughout the story is emphasizing the nature of the

relationship between the couple. She is no longer able to have a baby; and therefore, she is unable to find her lost identity, and thus she acts out of anger and jealousy pushed by her internal conflict.

Mrs. Wright is now eager enough to put an end to her torment. She decides to kill the phallic figure that stripped away her identity. Nevertheless, she uses not a gun, which is a phallic figure as well, but instead she uses a rope: "He died of rope round his neck," she kills him using the image of an embryo inside a womb, for the idea of a rope reminds us of the umbilical cord wrapped around the neck of the embryo. She kills her son who is her husband who is her foe. She is now setting on the throne. No longer of the male's tyranny. Now, she is free of the mental struggle within herself and able to laugh, for the fist of restriction over her mouth is finally removed.

To conclude, the real motive, as images of the bird, the cage, and fruit show, is the genetic lack of phallus (power and authority). Mrs. Wright is desperate to possess a phallic figure through either her husband or a male child but this would not happened. It is the penis envy, Freud speculates, that forces Mrs. Wright to commit a murder. It is her infantile, buried wish of independence and autonomy that put her to action. She retaliates by destroying her husband, the symbol of authority and power, which she lacks.

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